

When Family Plans Fail: Understanding the Social Consequences of Childlessness on Married Couples

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Abstract

The study examined the social impact of childlessness on married couples in the society. One objective and one research question alongside one hypothesis were raised for the study. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. A population of 160,301 women in 65 communities in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State was used. A sample of 100 women from 5 communities was used and this was done via multi-stage sampling technique of Random sampling technique and Proportionate sampling technique. The questionnaire titled "Socio-cultural Impact of Childlessness on Married Couples Questionnaire (SICMCQ)" was used as instrument to collect relevant data. The instrument was validated by some experts and its reliability was tested for to be 0.75. The data collected, were analyzed using frequency, mean and percentage for the research questions and Chi-square was used to test for the hypotheses. The findings from the study showed that the mean responses of the women on the social impact of childlessness on married couples in the society. From the analysis done, all the items with respective mean scores of 3.26, 3.04, 3.17 and 3.26 were accepted because their mean scores are above the criterion-mean score of 2.5. Based on the grand mean score obtained at 3.18, it can therefore be deduced that childlessness brings about a high level of negative social impacts on married couples in diverse ways.

Introduction

Approximately 70-80 million couples worldwide are currently infertile (Bos et al., 1995; Boivin et al., 2007) and it can be estimated that tens of millions of couples are primary infertile or childless. For most people, having children is immensely important; not being able to have children is a major life problem. There is also a large group of women and men, who have children, possibly from a previous relationship, who desperately want to have another child. A considerable body of research in Western countries has shown that involuntary childlessness has strong psychological consequences (see for reviews: Greil, 1997; Brokvich and Fisher, 1998). Most of the studies carried out in this domain are quantitative and some are qualitative. Both kind of studies, point in the same direction: there are various psychological and psychosomatic effects, and especially women are affected. The most frequently mentioned effects are distress, raised depression and anxiety levels, lowered self-esteem, feelings of blame and guilt, somatic complaints, and reduced sexual interest. For a small minority of women and

men in the Western world these effects are at a clinical level or can be considered extremely serious (Greil, 1997).

It is interesting that social and cultural consequences are seldom mentioned in the reports on these studies. When these aspects are considered, they are often related to studies about elderly people without children, regardless of the reason for being childless. It is stressed in the reports of these studies that frail old people without children have less social support (cf., Johnson, 2006) and a less robust network for independent living compared to old people with children (cf., Wenger et al., 2009). Wirtberg and co-workers (2007) however, carried out a study that is unique in the sense that it aims at elderly involuntarily childless women. They reported on 14 women, and described that in all cases but one sexual life was affected negatively and that half of these elderly childless women were separated.

Some studies, report the difficulty that childless couples have in communicating with friends who do have children. They describe negative (although sometimes well-meant) remarks within the couples' social worlds, for instance at birthday parties and other social gatherings; however, supportive reactions are also mentioned very often (Greil, 1991; van Balen et al., 1996; Schmidt, 2006). It is possible for childless couples to participate in the 'world of children', especially if couples have good friends or relatives who have children. They are able to participate in the lives and activities of the children of their friends and relatives by, for instance taking care of the children for a part of the week or when the parents are on holiday; taking the children to school, music lessons or sports activities; or going to games or shows in which the children participate. An early study on childlessness found that about ten per cent of couples had chosen this strategy as a way of coming to terms with their childless life (van Balen, 1991) Also, recently Wirtberg and colleagues (2007) described this as typical coping strategy for childlessness. It appears that in the West childless people are not formally excluded from being involved with raising children.

One of the major challenges confronting couples in the society is the issue of childlessness. Globally, and especially in Africa, when childlessness is mentioned, it draws attention and sympathy from those listening as they understand the heavy implications it has. As a consequence, fertility issues are one of the main reasons why couples seek gynecological advice in Nigeria. (Hajela et al, 2016). Couples who suffer from unintended childlessness may experience a significant psychosocial strain. There are many approaches to coping with the emotional effects of infertility. It is uncertain whether this psychological weight is the result of

infertility, existed before, or was brought on by infertility. If it is considered a consequence, a key question becomes what caused it: an inability to conceive, reproductive treatments, receiving a diagnosis, the stigma associated with being infertile, or the partner's behaviour. Childlessness has largely gone unnoticed by researchers, policy makers and programmers in developing countries, as the majority of their current programs are dedicated to population control.. There is therefore a serious need to examine the coping strategies order to minimize its effects on the society and also create more enabling ground for rapid development. Many studies concerning this topic have been conducted, primarily examining the distinctions between genders and presenting women's perspectives as the most important. Most writers agree that couples have a psychological influence on one another and experience infertility as a unified pair.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

To determine the social impact of childlessness on married couples in the society.

Research Question

What is the social impact of childlessness on married couples in the society?

Significance of the Study

To sociologists; the findings from this study will bring forth the weightiness of childlessness on married couples thereby engendering them to developing encouraging mechanisms to help them strive hard on this without being stressed or discouraged.

Scope of the Study

This study will strictly focus on examining socio-cultural and childlessness impact on married couples in the society. The target population for this study will comprise of married couples in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Definition of Terms

Childlessness: This refers to the inability of procuring an offspring.

Impact: This refers to the exacerbated influence an entity has on another.

Socio-Cultural Impact: This refers to the influence exerted by the society on another entity socially and culturally.

Married Couples: These are individuals that have decided to imbibe the duty of coming together to live as one legally, traditionally or religiously.

Causes of Childlessness of Married Couples in the Society

Medically, there are different causes and risk factors for couple's childlessness. According to Mustafa, Sharifa, Hadi, *et al.*(2019), infertility for men is most often caused by low or no sperm count and blockage of the tubes that transport sperm. Infertility in women on the other hand, is caused by a range of other factors such as problem with ovulation, blockage of fallopian tubes and physical damage to the uterus. Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STD), advanced age, smoking, and excess alcohol use are also mentioned as risk factors of infertility. However, a considerable number of people in the majority world have limited level of knowledge about the medical causes of infertility. The problem is thus usually perceived as caused by other factors than medical ones. Some associate infertility with supernatural powers and others associate it with diseases or with the absence of reproductive organs. A study by Fehintola, Fehintola, Ogunlaja, *et al.*(2017) on the social meaning of infertility in Southwest Nigeria showed that there are several traditional beliefs regarding the causes of infertility. Social scientists, however, are still debating the relative importance of voluntary and involuntary factors in the upturn in levels of childlessness, although individual self-fulfillment and freedom of choice have been seen as important (Egharevba, 2020). Okpan and Otega(2021) attributed the early part of the rise in childlessness mainly to voluntary factors "linked to broader changes

in the fabric of society regarding fertility control, contraceptive technology, female work preferences and patterns, and sexual and family norms". Low numbers of sperm are made and/or the sperm that are made do not work properly (Schenk, 2018). A number of factors can disrupt the production of sperm including undescended testis, infections such as mumps, heat, sperm antibodies, torsion, varicocele, drugs or radiation damage (Okpan&Otega,2021). Blockages (obstructions) in the tubes leading sperm away from the testes to the penis can cause a complete lack of sperm in the ejaculated semen. This accordingly is the second most common cause of male infertility and affects about three in every twenty infertile men, including men with the common problem of having an earlier vasectomy (Tabong & Adongo, 2013). In some men, sperm antibodies can develop which can lessen sperm movement and block egg binding during fertilisation. About one in every sixteen infertile men has sperm antibodies and this may cause male infertility (Tabong & Adongo, 2013). In women, poor quality eggs may cause infertility, a blocked fallopian tube could prevent the egg and sperm from uniting, or the woman may not ovulate regularly – a problem that is sometimes results in irregular menstrual cycle (Upadhyay, Chhabra & Nagar, 2020). There is a well-established link between a woman's age and infertility. Women over age 35 years have an estimated 50 percent chance of becoming pregnant naturally. As women age, their fertility is affected by the quantity and quality of their eggs (Saumet, Petropanagos, Buzaglo, *et al.*, 2018). In reality, the number of eggs available in the ovary gradually declines. As menopause approaches, an increasing number of cycles are not ovulatory, and therefore unable to result in conception (Q). Moreover, an older woman's eggs are most susceptible to chromosomal changes that may produce abnormal embryos.

Review of Related Empirical Studies

Okantey *et al.* (2021) in their study explored the socio-cultural implications of infertility in Ghana and the challenges couples encounter in accessing assisted reproductive technology.

Qualitative descriptive design was adopted for the study. A sample of 20 participants was purposely selected and used for the study. Theoretical analysis was done. It was revealed therein that culturally, couples who are unable to give birth are considered witches, discriminated against in decision making and are believed to be rejected by the ancestral world when they die. It was also found that these sociocultural implications of infertility compelled couples to access assisted reproductive technologies and were faced with social challenges, psychological implications, economic constraints, and medical complications. It was then concluded that children born through assisted reproductive technologies are not accepted by some sections of the society despite the challenges couples encounter in accessing these technologies. It was therefore recommended that public sensitization should be intensified in Ghana to accept the use of assisted reproductive technologies to limit stigmatization of couples with fertility problems and children born through assisted reproductive technology. Rasak and Oladipo (2017) in their study sought to investigate Childlessness and Its Socio-Cultural Implication on Married Couples within Some Selected Yoruba Communities in South-West Nigeria. Descriptive survey method was adopted for the study. Questionnaire was used for data collection. It was found out that not having children, whether voluntarily or not, contributes to a kind of invisibility and poverty in Nigeria. It concluded by noting a more tolerant attitude to in voluntary childlessness and then suggesting possible changes in perceptions of the condition.

Methodology

Research Design

The design of this study is the descriptive research design. This design is that which employs both qualitative and quantitative data for the proper dissemination of the stated questions that are formulated to dissolve the major purpose for this study. This research design was chosen

because of the purpose of the study to gather information on socio-cultural impact of childlessness on married couples in the society.

Population of the Study

The population for this study will comprise of women present in the 65 communities in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, which constitutes to a total estimation of 160,301 women (National Population Census, (2008) and World Sex Ratio (2021)).

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A multi-stage sampling technique of random sampling technique and proportionate sampling technique will be used for sample selection. Random sampling technique will be used in the selection of 5 communities out of the 65 communities in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State. Proportionate sampling technique will then be adopted in the selection of 20 women each in the chosen communities. A total sample of 100 women will then be given and used for the study, as stipulated in the table below:

Table 1: Sample Distribution

S/N	Districts	Sample Chosen
1	Choba	20
2	Rumueme	20
3	Ozuoba	20
4	Rumuokoro	20
5	Rumuigbo	20
Total		100

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument employed in this study is the questionnaire. It is a 20-item self-structure instrument titled “**Socio-cultural Impact of Childlessness on Married Couples Questionnaire (SICMCQ)**” that will be partitioned into two sections (A and B). Section A will cover the demographic aspect of it, which collects personal information about the respondents, while section B will cover the items, which elicited the responses of the respondents on each of the item statements present. The items are responded to with the aid of 4-point Likert scale of measurement of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

Method of Data Collection

Data will be collected using questionnaires. The researcher will go to the field and meet up with respondents, then hand out the copies of the questionnaire to them. These respondents will be given directives on how to go about the filling of the distributed instrument. After completion, the researcher will proceed to retrieve the distributed instrument immediately.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

Face and content validity of the instrument will be established by giving it to my supervisor and two other lecturers in the Department of Sociology. Their inputs will be ratified further by the supervisor, before its incorporation in the production the final draft of the questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument will be done through the test-retest method. This method is that which involves the administration of the instrument to a selected group of 20 women (outside the sample of the study but within the population of the study) with a separating time difference of 10 days between the two administrations. The responses gotten from the two

administrations will then be compared and correlated through the adoption of Pearson Product Moment Correlation, so as to arrive at the reliability co-efficient index of 0.75.

Method of Data Analysis

The data will be subjected to an analytical procedure with the aid of frequency, mean and percentage for the research questions. Chi-square will be used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The criterion-mean will be calculated for as follows:

Strongly Agree (SA) - 4points

Agree (A) - 3points

Disagree (D) - 2points

Strongly Disagree (SD) - 1point

$$\text{Criterion mean} = \frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.5$$

The item with a mean score that is up to and above the criterion mean will be “accepted” while the one with a mean score that is below the criterion mean will be “rejected”.

Results and Discussion

Results

Demographic Analysis

Table 1: Frequency and percentage of the demographics of women

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
20-29yrs	30	30%
30-39yrs	45	45%
40-49yrs	25	25%

50yrs & above	0	0%
Marital Status		
Single	25	25%
Married	55	55%
Divorced	15	15%
Widowed	5	5%
Separated	0	0%

From the analysis done above, it was displayed that 30% of the total sampled women are of 20-29yrs, 45% of the total sampled women are of 30-39yrs, 25% of the total sampled women are of 40-49yrs; 25% of the total sampled women are single, 55% of the total sampled women are married, 15% of the total sampled women are divorced while 5% of the total sampled women are widowed.

Analysis of Research Question

Research Question: What is the social impact of childlessness on married couples in the society?

Table 2: Mean statistics displaying the social impact of childlessness on married couples in the society

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Remark
5	Childlessness brings about criticism from others in the society.	36 (144)	54 (162)	10 (20)	0 (0)	3.26	Accepted
6	Childlessness makes one to feel less like a woman.	31 (124)	48 (144)	15 (30)	6 (6)	3.04	Accepted

7	Childlessness brings forth all manner of disrespect from both friends and families.	30 (120)	57 (171)	13 (26)	0 (0)	3.17	Accepted
8	Childlessness affects social standings in the society.	34 (136)	58 (174)	8 (16)	0 (0)	3.26	Accepted
Grand Mean						3.18	High

Data in the table above displayed the mean responses of the women on the social impact of childlessness on married couples in the society. From the analysis done, all the items with respective mean scores of 3.26, 3.04, 3.17 and 3.26 were accepted because their mean scores are above the criterion-mean score of 2.5. Based on the grand mean score obtained at 3.18, it can therefore be deduced that childlessness brings about a high level of negative social impacts on married couples in diverse ways.

Test for Hypothesis

Hypothesis: There is no significant impact of cultural perception of childlessness on married couples in the society.

Table 3: Summary of Chi-square analysis on the impact of social perception of childlessness on married couples in the society

Statement	N	df	X²cal	X²tab	Remark
Cultural perception Vs Childlessness among married couples	100	9	52.3457	16.919	Ho Rejected

Table 3 shows the result of the chi-square statistics on the impact of social perception of childlessness on married couples in the society. From the hypothesis testing done, it can be seen that $X^2_{cal.}$ is greater than X^2_{tab} thereby implying that the null hypothesis will be rejected. This therefore shows that there is a significant impact of cultural perception of childlessness on married couples in the society.

Discussion of Findings

On the cultural aspect, it was also revealed in analysis done in Tables 2 and 3 that there is a high level of negative cultural perception attributed to childlessness of married couples in the society and that childlessness brings about a high level of negative cultural impacts on married couples in diverse ways and that there is a significant impact of cultural perception of childlessness on married couples in the society. This was also backed up with the hypothesis testing done in Table 3 which connotes that there is a significant impact of cultural perception of childlessness on married couples in the society. This was corroborated with the findings of Dierickx, Rahbari, Longman, *et al.* (2018) who ascertained that childlessness can be a traumatic and worrying experience for men and women who for cultural or personal reasons, view childbearing as central to their live.

Summary and Conclusion

The study examined the socio-cultural impact of childlessness impact on married couples in the society. It was carried out with stipulated objectives. In actualizing this, several concepts have being reviewed for the better understanding of both the independent and dependent variables of the study and lots have been gathered childlessness and some factors that affect it and how impactful it can be on couples in the society by linking it socially and culturally. The whole study was compiled under five strategic chapters with each chapter having their inputs

to make towards the completion of this work, thereby implying one another as time goes by. With the first chapter covering the background that led to the carrying out of the work, the problem that can be cited as well as the objectives that are hoped to be achieved in the process of going about the tackling of the problems stated and the likes of it; the second chapter reviewing several past works that relates to this study; the third chapter stating the particular methodology that was adopted for the study; the fourth chapter going about the analyzing of the data that has been gathered and collated from the field to determine the purpose etched out for this study to investigate and then the fifth chapter serving as the concluding chapter of the study.

Recommendations

- 1) Policies should be generated towards protecting the rights of couples in the society, regardless of what they might be facing.
- 2) Measures should be directed towards the enhancement of medical facilities in the aide to curb the prevalence of childlessness in the society.

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